

Review of AI features to support mass deliberations

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Abstract. Democracy is based on dialogue/deliberation between equal citizens. Deliberative democracy enables citizens to participate in deliberations/discussion about issues affecting their lives. However, deliberations often face challenges related to low participation, exclusion, low-quality contributions and difficult moderation. AI potentially can address many of these challenges. For example, AI can facilitate deliberations by moderating discussions, processing deliberation data (e.g., summarizing) and enhancing participation. However, the integration of AI into deliberations also raises risks related to fairness and transparency. This paper presents a review of existing research that explores the role of AI in mass deliberations. The aim is to identify AI features that can enhance deliberations, exploring also potential benefits and risks. We anticipate that the findings can contribute to the ongoing debate on the future role of AI in political deliberations.

Keywords: AI features · mass deliberations · review · deliberative democracy · risks

1 Introduction

Democracy is based on dialogue/deliberation between equal citizens. Deliberative democracy enables citizens to participate in deliberations/discussion on issues affecting their lives. The involvement can be done through various deliberative processes in which citizens can discuss, present their opinions, provide arguments, and ultimately reach consensus.

However, implementing deliberative democracy in practice at scale faces various barriers such as under representation or low-participation and low quality discourse. Towards this problem definition, online participation platforms seems promising in order to facilitate mass deliberations, however there is ample empirical evidence that they fall short suffering from low participation, opaque processes and low-quality citizens contributions[34][35].

In this context, Artificial intelligence (AI), especially Large Language Models (LLMs), are emerging as potential tools to address these challenges by improving scalability, quality and accessibility of deliberations. AI can support various functions including moderation of discussions, processing of deliberation data (e.g., summarizing) etc.

In the current literature, there is an increased interest in AI-supported deliberations, however the literature remains fragmented. There is no unified framework to clarify the applied features and their alignment with existing deliberation processes. This fragmentation motivates the need for a relevant literature review. The need is more highlighted by the rapidly expanding popularity and capabilities of AI and especially LLMs. In this context, this paper offers a structured review aiming to identify current research about AI features that can be used to enhance deliberations exploring also their potential benefits and risks. The main research questions that we aim to tackle are:

- Which foundational democratic values need to be considered when integrating AI in political deliberations?
- How can AI facilitate mass deliberations?
- What are the potential risks associated with the use of AI in political deliberations?

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents some background information about the deliberative processes and their variations/decision that need to be considered; section 3 presents the methodology used for the review; section 4 presents the main results of the paper including the identified AI features, the democratic values which need to be considered when integrating AI in political deliberations and the potential risks associated with the use of AI in political deliberations; finally section 5 includes a discussion and conclusion.

2 Background

This section presents some background information about existing deliberative processes, their stages and some variants/decision that need to be considered. This information is foundational in order to understand in the later sections, how AI can fit in these processes.

2.1 Deliberative processes

Deliberations can be done following various deliberative processes/methods. Table 1 presents an indicative list of deliberative processes/methods. Some methods rely on random selection of participants (e.g., civic lottery, citizen jury) to ensure fairness and diversity. Regarding the profile of the participants, some methods involve expert-driven discussions (Deliberative Delphi) while others involve public dialogues (World Café). Informed participation is also core principle, often requiring pre-deliberation education (Deliberative Polling, Citizens' Initiative Review). Variations occur also based on the group size (small juries vs. large

Table 1. Indicative list of deliberation processes/methods

Deliberation processes/method	pro-	Description
Deliberative poling [15]		Randomly selected citizens express their opinion by answering a specific survey before and after participating at deliberation processes (discussions). Special emphasis is given to appropriately inform the citizens in advance.
Deliberative Delphi [21]		A qualitative method for expert consultations and surveys, characterized by mini-workshops and debate/role-play for emotional engagement and cognitive bias reduction.
World cafe [30]		People are discussing about various topics. These discussions are made up of a small number of citizens who change groups at regular intervals so that opinions are shared.
Citizen jury [38]		Representative randomly selected small group of citizens that attend on hearings for a short period of time and then they deliberate and announce their decisions/recommendations.
Civic lottery [17]		Is a lottery-based technique by which a fair and representative sample for randomly selecting citizens to participate in a deliberative process to obtain a representative sample. This is a component of other methodologies.
Citizens' initiatives reviews [18]	re-	Involves a randomly selected representative panel who deliberate about a proposed law or constitutional amendment put into referendum.

groups) and format (static groups vs. rotating discussions). In some cases large groups can be separated to many smaller ones (e.g., deliberative poling).

The deliberative processes presented in table 1 comprise mainly three generic stages:

- Preparatory Stage: This involves the definition of the deliberation theme and the selection/engagement of the participants. This stage may also include the education of citizens on the deliberation theme, thus enabling them to make more informed contributions.
- Deliberation Stage: This is the main stage where citizens participate in discussions, express their opinion, provide arguments, hear the opinions of others and ideally achieve consensus on a theme.
- Post-Processing Stage: After deliberation, this stage involves summarizing or synthesizing the content produced during the deliberations (e.g., positions, arguments). It may also include the communication of the results.

2.2 Deliberative processes variations/decisions

The deliberative processes revolve around multiple dimensions/decisions, which vary depending on the structure and context of the discussion. How each di-

mension/decision is approached lies in the hands of the deliberation organizers, potentially resulting in numerous variations of the overall process. The following paragraphs outline the possible approaches to each decision point.

Deliberation size (mini-public vs mass deliberations): in mini-public a representative group of citizens is randomly selected and is deliberating, advising, or deciding for the specific issue. This is an umbrella term for many deliberative processes. In contrast, mass deliberations involve a large number of participants engaging in discussion within a single space. To improve manageability and effectiveness large number of participants can be separated into many smaller groups.

Asynchronous vs. synchronous deliberation: Synchronous deliberation occurs in real-time, allowing for live interaction and immediate responses (e.g., live debates, video conferences). While, asynchronous deliberations (e.g., online forums) may be held over a longer period of time, enabling participants to contribute at their own convenience.

Online vs. Offline Deliberation: deliberations can be either online or offline. Offline deliberations include traditional face-to-face interaction in physical spaces and can strengthen direct interaction and trust. However they have limitation related to location, time and availability constraints. On the other hand online deliberations (can be synchronous e.g., live video discussions, chat-based platforms, or asynchronous e.g., forums) are conducted through digital platforms and facilitate large-scale participation across geographic boundaries. However, online deliberations phase challenges such as misinformation and representatives.

Anonymous vs. non-anonymous deliberation: deliberations can be either anonymous or non-anonymous. In anonymous deliberations participants do not reveal their name/identity. This approach can enable more honest contributions, reduce social pressure, and minimize biases related participants' profiles (e.g., gender, education, background). However, anonymous deliberations may also lead to reduced trust, and are more vulnerable to malicious behavior (e.g., trolls or misinformation attacks). On the other hand, in non-anonymous deliberations participants reveal their name (either to all participants or to the deliberation organizer). This approach increases trust and a sense of responsibility in discussions. However, this may also prevent marginalized people/group to participate. The choice between anonymous and non-anonymous deliberations depends on the goal and the theme of the deliberation. For example, the goal of some deliberations may be to provide recommendations/suggestions to policymakers. In this case open anonymous deliberations can be used. While other deliberations may lead to binding decisions, in this case non-anonymous deliberations may be preferred.

Deliberation modality (text vs. video/audio deliberation): deliberations may use either text or video/audio interactions. Text deliberations involve written contributions (e.g., online forums, chat platforms). Some benefits of text based deliberations include the fact that participants have more time to think carefully and make better arguments. They are also more easily accessible providing a record of discussions. However, they may be more "boring" and cumbersome

than audio/video. On the other hand, video/audio deliberations involve live or recorded communication that enable more dynamic and expressive discussions. They also more engaging for participants, especially young people. However, they require more advanced technology (e.g., Video LLMs) and resources and can be harder to moderate (e.g., coordinate times for live participation). The choice between text and video/audio depends on the desired level of engagement, the type of discussion, and the available resources.

3 Methodology

The literature review of this paper followed PRISMA guidelines and employed a multi-stage process to synthesize our research. A search was conducted in two databases: Scopus and Web of Science. The search query applied to both databases was: (*"Large Language Models" OR "NLP" OR "AI" OR "Machine Learning"*) AND (*deliberation OR consultation OR "online deliberation" OR "democracy" OR "citizen participation"*). The search was limited only to recent publications (>2021) and applied subject area filters. In Scopus the categories included were: Computer Science, Social Sciences, Engineering, and Decision Sciences, resulting in 1,608 papers. In Web of Science, with similar timeline and categories (Computer Science, Engineering, Social Sciences, and Other), we retrieved 435 papers. For Scopus we ordered the results based on relevance and selected the top 500. After combining the remaining results of both databases we removed 112 duplicates. From the resulting 823 articles, we excluded 575 as out of scope, for example papers focused on applications of machine learning in healthcare. More exclusions (216 articles) were made for papers that were too general or not entirely aligned with our research. This process resulted in 20 core papers. We also incorporated 7 relevant papers identified through snowball search of citations within the 20 core papers. Finally, 5 more papers were added from grey literature (general web search for absolutely relevant papers). As a result a total number of 32 papers were included in this review. The overall PRISMA methodology is depicted at figure 1.

4 Results

This section presents the main results of the study including the identified foundational values that need to be considered when integrating AI political deliberations (sub-section 4.1), the AI features to augment/facilitate mass deliberations (sub-section 4.2) and the risks associated with the use of AI in political deliberations (sub-section 4.3).

4.1 Foundational Values for using AI in Political Deliberations

As a result of the analysis we identified some main democratic values that need to be considered when incorporating AI features in political deliberations. The following paragraphs present these values.

Fig. 1. PRISMA methodology of the review.

Preserving Agency and Autonomy: A fundamental principle in democratic practices involves enabling people to express their choices in the construction of the future of their societies. Thus, it is important to focus on approaches where citizens participate meaningfully, with AI augmenting and not reducing that agency [14, 20, 3, 40, 16].

Encouraging Mutual Respect: Deliberative processes need to rely on mutual understanding (i.e., listen to opposing ideas, present arguments). In a context such as online deliberations, care should be taken to promote and enable understanding and tolerance among participants [14, 3].

Promoting Equality and Inclusiveness: Enable people that often do not take part in deliberations to do so. This can be done by allowing open participation to previously marginalized groups e.g., due to geographical, economical, educational, or health status [3, 11, 25].

4.2 AI features to facilitate mass deliberations

AI (including LLMs) have many capabilities, which can be applied to various parts of the deliberation processes offering new opportunities including for example the maximization of participation or the improvement of the deliberation content/contributions. This section presents the identified AI features that can augment/facilitate mass deliberations. The identified AI features are categorized based on the stage of the deliberative process (described in section 2.1) that they can facilitate. Some AI features can be applied to more than one stage. For example summarization of deliberation content can be applied both at the deliberation stage (summarize the current deliberations status), and at the post-processing stage (summarize the final deliberation status). Such AI features are included at the stage that is more reasonable in our understanding. An important finding of our review is that very few AI feature is currently used (or proposed to be used) for the preparatory stage.

The reviewed articles explore a wide range of AI features both from a theoretical view point (proposed features) and practical applications involving various AI technologies such as Generative AI, LLMs, NLP, chatbots etc. The proposed functionalities include among others the assessing of the quality of contributions, achieving consensus, AI enhanced moderation of discussions, fact-checking, identify harmful content etc. The following paragraphs describe in detail the AI features identified for each stage of the deliberative process, while table 2 provides an overview.

AI features for the preparatory deliberation stage Generating Groups: Based on various insights (including on specific opinions shared, backgrounds, stated preference in past engagements) AI models, including more traditional NLP approaches [3], may enable identification of groups based on different characteristics.

AI features for the deliberation stage Considering the complex nature of deliberations (i.e., complex conversations, arguments, positions), the effective facilitation or moderation is essential, as it can ensure outputs of higher quality and fairer participation. A variety of AI features can be applied in this context:

- Automated Moderator: AI (including LLMs) can serve as a moderator which regulates turn-taking during online discussions to encourage more equitable participation and reduce bias by any few “louder” participants [32, 28].
- Speaking Queue Enforcement (Video Deliberation): AI can also aid a structured speaking queue to avoid biases. Users can be guaranteed speaking time while helping organize the deliberations and avoid the common scenario where one participant overtakes the conversation by constantly speaking, thereby limiting exposure of opinions in groups [14].
- Combating Harmful Content: AI (including chatbots and LLMs) can facilitate asynchronous deliberation by detecting potentially harmful content [1, 36, 6, 28]. This feature can for example limit the spread of misinformation

acting as a complement to traditional fact-checking and moderation methods.

- Detecting toxic behavior: Similar to the above (Combating Harmful Content) but for synchronous (live) deliberations. In this case AI for example may block a user [14].
- Identify stalls in live conversations: In this case AI may advance the agenda to the next item [14].
- Real-Time Translation: In settings where deliberations occur among participants using different languages, AI (LLMs) can facilitate seamless transitions between languages [37, 25, 32, 27, 28]. For example it can present output in desired languages or actively moderate conversations. This feature enables cross-cultural communication and inclusion.
- Fact-checking: AI can identify and address factuality, providing verifiable information while also allowing counter points to emerge and get presented [20, 2, 26, 23, 29, 28].
- Consensus building: Based on AI (LLM) assisted analysis the system can propose potential points to align on with other members. AI can also assist groups that struggle in achieving consensus by proposing routes/areas to bridge disagreement or make progress [37, 39, 12, 5, 8, 32, 28].
- Comment Routing: The complex nature of a public online deliberation generates many content (comments) that cannot easily be processed by humans. AI (LLMs) can "route" content to the "best fit" person within deliberation. This could maximize impact while reducing time cost and complexity for individual users [37, 14].
- Identifying High-Potential Ideas: AI (LLMs) can detect "viral" or insightful information/ideas that gain the interest of multiple users. Those ideas can be promoted, thus reducing the risk that high-potential ideas get neglected or seen by a limited number of participants [37, 28].
- Assisting with content generation: Participants of deliberations may feel like passive students rather than active collaborators. AI (LLMs) can assist participants to formulate questions or assist in generating ideas/comments [7]. Afterwards, participants can engage and build upon these suggestions to keep the dialogue going on in a more productive way [32, 4].
- Monitor deliberative quality: AI (LLMs) can analyze deliberation content in real-time and thus facilitate the monitoring of the deliberative quality [28]. AI models could provide invaluable feedback to facilitators. For example, AI could identify and highlight instances that either promote or hinder constructive dialogue. This live-time analysis can enable facilitators to address shortcomings as they emerge leading to richer and more effective deliberative processes [32, 19]. AI can also support the generation of indicators related to the process that can be subsequently monitored [10].
- Playing devil's advocate: AI (LLMs) can also enhance the quality of deliberation outputs by acting as a devil's advocate. AI can generate objections and challenge emerging consensus. In this way AI can mitigate the risk of group-think and promote more critical judgments. However, this functionality may raise the risk of pushing specific perspectives. To avoid this, AI-generated

content should be framed as open-ended questions without directing participants' opinions [32].

AI features for the post-processing deliberation stage The large amount of complex data produced through deliberations requires processing in order to provide useful insights. In this direction, AI provides a number of features that have already been applied in several cases. The processing of deliberation data can occur both during the deliberation (in order to get a sense of the current deliberation state) and after the deliberation. We consider the post-processing as more common, however both of them are applicable. The following paragraphs present the relevant AI functionalities:

- Summarizing Information: AI (LLMs and more traditional NLP approaches) can support the automatic production of informative summaries and reports. Such techniques have value by automatically transforming large amounts of unstructured data into short summaries for citizens or policy-makers [37, 3, 9, 27, 32].
- Simplifying information: AI (LLMs and more traditional NLP approaches) can take complex human language and simplify it [33, 32]. In [13] authors found that LLMs were as effective as human annotators in simplifying sentences. While in [4] an LLM was employed to rephrase user messages in a more polite manner.
- Topic Modeling: AI (LLMs and more traditional NLP approaches) can facilitate clustering similar points and identifying key topics that are part of the discussions. This allows to focus on crucial aspects that have emerged during deliberation, giving a more solid picture of discussions [37, 9, 27, 3, 41].
- Clustering and organizing arguments: AI could help cluster arguments in an organized way. In this way, the contributions of large amounts of people can actually be reduced to a manageable amount of content. This could be done in real time to help move the deliberation forward or afterwards to make sense of a large amount of data produced [28, 36].
- Entity/relation Extraction: The ability to structure unstructured text by detecting underlying entities/relations. For example, LLMs can identify specific government departments [20].
- Visualization: AI generated output may come with options to e.g., show agreements and disagreement areas on charts, or map users opinions over an argument. This for example could help participants to identify areas of disagreement that needs to be explored [37].
- Acting as question and answer systems (chatbot): AI can be used as question and answer systems providing information to participants on demand based on the content produced during the deliberation. This for example means that AI could be available at any time to support participant learning when relevant experts are not present [32].
- Aggregating across deliberation: Aggregating data from multiple deliberation groups is a significant challenge for deliberations that can limit their scalability. In this context, AI (LLMs) can process aggregated data among

deliberation groups e.g., cluster viewpoints/arguments, identify agreements or disagreements [32].

- Support effective communication: AI can facilitate communication with the wider public during the follow-up phase of the deliberation. AI can facilitate a more personalized communication strategy tailored to the needs of various groups. For example, LLMs can create different text versions to engage specific audiences [32].

4.3 Risk associated with the use of AI in political deliberations

This section presents a number of risk that have been identified and are associated with the use of AI in political deliberations.

Bias: AI systems often include bias in the output they produce [22][24]. This may result, for example, in excluding some sections of society (e.g. minorities, individuals of different backgrounds), or some proposals prioritized over others. Thus, it is important that AI systems use techniques to limit bias e.g., use AI models that reflect public preferences, or data-sampling methods or explicit algorithmic corrections to minimize the bias effect.

Hallucination: Another risk of AI is “hallucination” that produces meaningless information. A potential solution is to compare expert and (aggregated) public opinions in deliberation. In this way content generated by AI can be assessed. Additionally, human oversight is also needed to detect/correct errors especially when AI is trained on low-quality data [37, 20].

Substitution vs Augmentation: Another risk that arises is related to the use of AI to substitute humans [31]. This may reduce the required human effort, however it also neglects several aspects (e.g., active participation, engagement) that are core for quality deliberations [37]. On the other hand, when AI augments deliberation processes it allows greater individual autonomy. The challenge here is to enable augmentation but not lead to complete automation of deliberative processes. This will enable engaging participants by providing deeper insights and not treating them as passive recipients of the results.

Loss of Context and Human Connection: AI based deliberation processes can miss important human elements needed for meaningful participation e.g., tone of voice, body language, empathy etc. These elements help build trust between humans and foster engagement. Thus, relying only on AI risks making discussions feel mechanical, reducing human interaction and participation [2]. In the moment, such elements cannot be efficiently replicated by AI.

5 Discussion and conclusion

This paper reviewed current research related to role of AI role in political deliberations. The results identified both useful AI features but also risks and foundational democratic values that need to be considered. AI provides various features to address existing challenges in deliberative democracy (e.g., low

Table 2. Identified AI features to support mass deliberations

AI feature	Description
Preparatory stage	
Generating Groups	Identifies groups based on various characteristics, potentially revealing hidden power dynamics
Deliberation stage	
Automated Moderator	Manages turn-taking to ensure more equitable participation, preventing domination by individuals.
Speaking Queue Enforcement	Guarantees speaking time for all participants preventing one person from taking over the conversation.
Combating Harmful Content	Facilitate asynchronous deliberation by detecting potentially harmful content
Detect toxic behavior	Similar to "Combating Harmful Content" for live deliberations.
Identify stalls in live conversations	In this case AI may advance the agenda to the next item
Real-Time Translation	Enables real-time communication among participants speaking different languages via automated translation.
Fact-checking	Identifies and addresses factuality, providing verified information and allowing for counter points to emerge and get presented.
Consensus building	Proposes suggestions and ways for users to align on common ground and bridges disagreements to move toward consensus.
Comment Routing	Ensures all views are considered by routing comments to the appropriate individuals within the deliberation.
Identifying High-Potential Ideas	Highlight/promote "viral" or insightful information/ideas that gain the interest of multiple users.
Assisting with content generation	AI can assist participants to formulate questions or assist in generating content.
Monitor deliberative quality	AI can analyze deliberation in real-time, providing feedback to facilitators to improve discussion quality and inclusivity.
Playing devil's advocate	AI can act as devil's advocates by challenging consensus and fostering critical thinking (open-ended questions to avoid bias).
Post-processing stage	
Summarizing Info	AI can support the automatic production of informative summaries and reports.
Simplifying info	AI can take complex human language and simplify it.
Topic Modeling	Clusters similar points and identifies key categories in discussions, aiding comprehension and focusing on essential aspects.
Clustering and organizing arguments	AI could cluster arguments in an organized and meaningful way reducing the content to a manageable amount.
Visualization	Displays data and patterns of opinions via visualizations.
Acting as question and answer systems	AI can be used as question and answer systems providing information to participants on demand.
Aggregating across deliberation	AI can synthesize large amounts of deliberation data from multiple deliberation groups.
Support effective communication	AI can enhance communication of the deliberation outcomes with the wider public during the follow-up phase.

participation, difficult moderation, low quality contributions, information overload). It can improve moderation, facilitate consensus building, detect harmful content, summarize content etc. However, there are also significant risks e.g., bias, transparency, loss of human agency, that need to be considered.

Our finding also highlight that AI features currently support the deliberation and the post-processing stages, while the preparatory stage is neglected. The preparatory stage is important in order to educate and engage participants. Thus strengthening AI support in this stage could enhance the quality of deliberations.

Based on the review there are some trade-offs that need to be considers when adopting AI in mass deliberations. One trade-off is between efficiency and citizen empowerment. AI can facilitate deliberative processes, making them more accessible and manageable at scale. For example, AI moderation, summarization or translation can increase participation and facilitate the processing of big deliberation data. However, this AI-based efficiency could reduce citizen empowerment making citizens fill excluded or unfamiliar with the deliberative processes and unable to understand/influence the outcomes.

A related trade-off is between AI autonomy and human oversight. AI should be used carefully ensuring the preservation of autonomy of human oversight in various AI features (e.g., moderation, reporting and translations). A question that arises is which activities should be done by humans, and which could be better done via AI. Another critical questions is, where does facilitation end and control begin? Ideally, AI should be used as an augmentation tool rather than a tool for complete automation.

AI offers promising features to facilitate mass deliberations, however their application must be carefully designed to align with democratic values. There must be safeguards ensuring that AI augments deliberative processes and not completely substitutive humans. As AI is evolving in a rapid way new features may arise that could be used to facilitate political deliberations. Such features must be carefully assessed to maximize benefits while mitigating risks.

Considering the adoption of AI in deliberative democracy, it is important to balance technological innovation and ethical responsibility. We anticipate that this review paper will contribute towards this direction and its findings can contribute to the ongoing debate on the future role of AI in deliberative democracy.

Acknowledgments. Funded by the European Union under grant agreement No. 101178806. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. .

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